

IDENTIFICATION OF INFLUENCE FACTORS ON UNIVERSITY PROJECTS DURING THE SARS COV 2 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper aims to identify the factors that exert a significant influence on the members of project teams developed in universities, planning their activities and factors and carrying out the activities of the project teams under the conditions of the SARS COV 2 pandemic.*

Methodology/approach – *In order to carry out the research, specific aspects in the management of human resources were individualized within the projects regarding human resource planning.*

Findings – *The present research refers to the management of human resources in Romanian university projects from the point of view of the influencing factors of human resources planning under the conditions of the pandemic.*

Research limitations/implications – *Social distancing, as a measure during the COVID 19 period, determined the forcing of global digitization, implicitly the activities within the projects, which according to the initial planning, should have been carried out face to face, were cancelled.*

Practical implications – *The results of the research could be of interest to project managers, human resources managers, other categories of professionals whose activities concern the sphere of human resources.*

Originality/value – *The study captures a series of problems and restrictions faced by the management of human resources within the projects carried out in higher education institutions in Romania, during the pandemic period.*

Key words: COVID 19, SARS COV 2, Human resource management

Introducere

Economic studies demonstrate the quality of higher education and vocational training is essential for economies that intends to adopt the value chain beyond simple manufacturing processes (Tanase & Tanase, 2011). Globalization has required the employment of trained personnel, able to adapt to the environment, a fact proven during the COVID 19 pandemic.

Human resource management has evolved from the „personnel” function to the strategic human resource management function (Deadrick & Stone, 2014). The human resource planning activity within the projects was also propelled along this trajectory, as a function of human resource management. The study aims to identify the factors with a significant influence on human resource management within university projects under pandemic conditions.

The research on the management of human resources in Romanian university projects, influencing factors of human resources planning under the conditions of the COVID 19 pandemic, had the following objectives:

- Identification of the factors with significant influence on the human resource within the university projects
- Planning the activities of the participants in the project teams
- Factors in carrying out activities for project team members during the SARS COV 2 pandemic

- Evaluation and quantitative analysis of human resources management in Romanian university projects, influencing factors of human resources planning in pandemic conditions
- Designing a model regarding the human resources management of the projects, with the objective: The need to identify, rank and complete the factors that exert a significant influence on the human resource.

Any scientific work must be based on a well-established plan, which respects a working model (Lupu, Rusu, Oniciuc, & Rusu, 2006). The methodological plan for the research went through the following stages:

- Identification of the influencing factors of human resources planning
- Development of research tool
- Choosing and describing the sample
- Data collection
- Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the collected data
- Synthesizing the information obtained
- Reporting

In the research, the techniques and tools of search and data collection used was the questionnaire survey, through which the quantitative research was carried out.

I designed a questionnaire structured on sections:

- the need to identify the factors under the conditions of the pandemic
- identifying the influences of the factors on the human resources management of the projects
- researching the influence of factors on the management and planning of human resources in the specific conditions of the pandemic.

In modern times the health, morale and motivation of employees are important factors when an organization deals with crises. Managers must adopt measures to maintain employee trust, not only during crises, but also in normal life conditions (Vardarlier, 2016).

In 1954 Abraham Maslow published the pyramid of needs. The needs are instinctive, as they climb the pyramid, they manifest themselves depending on the degree of education and the personality of each individual. The spread of the COVID 19 pandemic generated restrictions of an economic, social, cultural and last but not least health nature. It has been observed that within Maslow's pyramid, the need for digital technology is imposed, a necessity that falls on any of the steps, tending towards the base of the pyramid.

The Authority for the Digitization of Romania was established in 2020, with the role of coordinating the implementation of strategies and policies in the field of digital transformation and the information society, in accordance with European policy (Commission, 2021).

In order to ensure the necessary human resources in the development and realization of university projects, in pandemic conditions, a rigorous planning of the activities carried out exclusively online was necessary.

Table no I the problems identified, generated by factors with significant influence on human resource in higher education institutions, are reproduced.

Internal and external factors can have a negative impact on the project, can delay or lead to its noncompletion. The project manager has the task of risk analysis, in order to prevent possible problems.

Personnel planning (Prodan, 2011) involves identifying the future needs of the organization and determining the number of employees that must be recruited by the organization at a given time.

Table no I. Identification of human resources problems in the university and projects under the influence of some factors.

Factors of influence	Problems identified
Internal factors	
Diversity of training and concerns	-The research activity, as well as the administrative one, are carried out in parallel directions, the staff do not interact -The activity of the project teams is carried out independently of the basic function, or they can be carried out identically with the tasks of the basic function, by activity categories according to the Gantt chart
Level of expertise	-In higher education, expertise is very well established in the field of employment skills and through annual evaluations. -Within the projects, the experience accumulated throughout the career is personal, it can only be valued by coopting and working in teams
Ways of selecting team participans from the univerity's point of view	-The selection is made on the basis of the internal procedures regarding the human resources policy of the institution, in conjunction with the national legislation -For projects, the selection is made according to manuals, guides, internal and international instructions aligned with Romanian legislation
External factors	
The SARS COV 2 pandemic	-Limiting measures and even bans on leaving were imposed homes, by military orders in the state of emergency and then in the state of alert -Sets of rules regarding social distancing were issued, so interviews, work meetings, mobility on projects were cancelled -Online platforms had to be identified, resources for paying subscriptions, purchasing software and hardware for running activities exclusively in the online environment
Budget constraints	-Often the budgets are not enough, a problem that leads to great sacrifices in order not to compromise on quality -They are imposed and generate an interdependence between the weight of direct expenses versus indirect ones
Human resource funding restrictions	-These restrictions lead to the loading of the basic norm, by carrying out additional activities of the nature of projects -Certain projects did not provide a budget for financing human resources. Through volunteer work, team members are not motivates to get involved in this type of activity
Restrictions of the number of participans in the team	-The need to fulfill some activities is created, which lead to overwork of team members
Restrictions on team structure	-The lack of a staff with certain functions and expertise, leads to the execution of some activities by learning „on the go” by the team members, who become overcrowded
Restrictions on the periodic evaluation of human resource activities	-Evaluating activities late, or not at all, is reflected in sentimental frustration regarding the reward

Following Romanian's integration into the European Union, it was noticed that the activities are oriented towards the absorption of funds, so the universities have transposed the Standards into their own work procedure.

As part of the Research on specific aspects in human resource management of human resource planning projects, normative acts were studied find out about: notions about types of projects; projects life cycle; how to identify a problem; target group and beneficiaries; the purpose and objectives of the projects; the activities; results, impact and indicators; risk managemen; monitoring and evolution; budget; the sustainability plan. The pandemic has attracted extreme military and civilian measures: social distancing and the orientation of all activities only in the online environment.

The evaluation stage and quantitative analysis regarding management of human resources in Romanian university projects, influencing factors of human resources planning under the conditions of pandemic restrictions was carried out as follows:

- to determine the aspects regarding the quality of human resources planning, the exploratory research techniques consisted in consulting the specialized literature, internal documentation: procedures, decisions, service notes, job descriptions, as well as external: guides, manuals, legislation and last but not least, online interviews with managers of different structures, employees of the human resources department.
- investigating the links between the most important factors that exert a significant influence on the human resource within higher education institutions and the aspects regarding human resources planning.

The Questionnaire created and distributed through the Google Form application was used, in August 2021, applied to 44 managers and members of project teams, or employees of prestigious universities in Romania.

The questionnaire was structured: General characteristics; Human resource planning in accessed projects; Factors influencing human resources planning under the conditions of the pandemic; Expected results.

Following the processing of the sample data in the SPSS Statistics application, the respondents identified external factors disrupting the activity, and the analysis of the variables for human resource planning in projects accessed by the university, we reproduce some sequences:

Table no II. In the conditons of some critical situations at a global level in the last decade, from the economic crisis to the crises generate by pandemic COVID 19 your activity did it suffer in conection with projects ?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	30	68,2	68,2	68,2
no	13	29,5	29,5	97,7
I do not know	1	2,3	2,3	100,0
Total	44	100,0	100,0	

Table no II 68.2 percent of respondents say that their own activity was influenced by COVID, 29.5 percent of respondents say that their own activity was not influenced by COVID, and 2.3 percent do not know.

3. CARE SUNT PRINCIPALII FACTORI INTERNI CARE V-AU PERTURBAT ACTIVITATEA PE PROIECTE?

32 responses

Figure no 1. The respondents identified as internal factors disrupting the activity: 46.9 percent the diversity of training and concerns, 21.9 percent the level of expertise, 31,3 percent affirm that the method of selection, and 28.1 percent see other factors.

5. CARE SUNT PRINCIPALII FACTORI EXTERNI CARE AU PERTURBAT ACTIVITATEA DVS. PE PROIECTE?

37 responses

Figure no 2. The external respondents disrupting the activity identified : 83,8 percent noted the restrictions imposed by the funding source, 51.4 percent the budget restrictions, 45,9 percent surprised restrictions regarding financing, 27.0 percent were influenced by the number of participants in team, 24.3 percent were disturbed by restrictions regarding the team structure, and 21.6 percent are affected by the evaluation, and 10.8 percent invoke other effects.

Analyzing the results after applying the questionnaire, the following aspects were distinguished:

General characteristics: the questionnaire was addressed to the project managers, or members of university project teams, to which 44 respondents answered. We can state that the respondents have a seniority of 10-15 years to over 25 years; with higher education: bachelor's degree, master's degree, doctorate and postdoctorate; aged between 26 and over 65 years.

From the point of view of human resource planning in accessed projects , recruitment, selection, and hiring per project will be carried out, after a careful analysis of the human resource policy and the budget regarding personnel expenses. Recruitment is done by the department involved in the realization of the project both from the internal and external environment.

In the section: Influencing factors of human resources planning in the conditions of funding failures and the COVID 19 pandemic: 68.2 percent of the respondents stated that project activity suffered due to interna land external factors, among which we list: the rigidity of the conditions imposed by the projects regarding human resources, delayed financing, legislative restrictions regarding the time worked on the projects, implicitly the salary and last but not least, the restrictions imposed by the pandemic.

In the Expected results section: the interviewees considered that they fulfilled their mission in the realization of the projects, as members of the teams, even from the external environment of the university. It has been demonstrated that a correctly made planning ensures the necessary human resources to achieve the objectives and complete the projects.

Within the Research on specific aspects in human resource management of human resource planning projects, it was taken into account that the disturbances caused by COVID 19, in all fields of activity, were manifested at a global level. The entities were affected financially, operationally and personally, a situation in which they looked for solutions to continue their activity, and the long term to obtain increases. Postpandemic conditions of stress and despair could create opportunities for illegal and fraudulent activities.

The design of a model regarding the human resources management of projects, having as its objective the need to identify, prioritize and complete the factors that exert a significant influence on the human resource under the conditions of the SARS COV 2 pandemic, as a suport for the interested factors.

The personal contribution consisted in the creation of a comparative model based on comparison criteria between project human resources management planning and university human resources

management, under the conditions of the pandemic. Establishing on the basis of the job descriptions and the responsibilities of the university human resources management personnel, the activities of the personnel compatible with the members of the project team, of specific tasks related to the project that can periodically be entered in the job descriptions.

Conclusions

In the current context of the pandemic and postpandemic period, **the Authority for the Digitization of Romania** has issued strategies and policies for the implementation of digitization. As a result, universities have redefined their objectives by adapting both the teaching process and research, respectively the development of projects to the online environment.

The study undertaken specific aspects in the human resources management of the human resource planning projects, beyond the social, economic and health blockages, forcing a series of restrictive measures. But the planning was imperatively necessary to ensure the qualified human resource and to identify reserves of specialists, who contributed to the completion and validation of each stage of the projects. Through the care of the project managers, a risk analysis was made to evaluate the problems caused by internal and external factors on the projects, with the observation that poor planning can contribute to the failure of the project.

The analysis regarding human resource planning indicated that the criteria regarding specialization, homogeneity of teams, qualification of project team members, participation in various projects and work procedures were revised and adapted to ensure the achievement of project objectives.

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